

Artificial Intelligence Management Procedures

PRECINCT

Standard and Recommendation Guidelines

AI for Critical Infrastructure Protection – Guidance on the
implementation of AI-based products

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Foreword

This document is the result of a collaboration among PRECINCT project partners with the aim of standardizing the adoption, implementation, and integration of artificial intelligence (AI) technologies in the protection of critical infrastructures.

Introduction

The purpose of this document is to provide guidelines that improve the trustworthiness of AI-based products. Although it is mainly intended for critical infrastructure protection (CIP), the principles identified may apply to any AI-based products. The document describes many aspects around AI tool development including normative references, potential challenges, data management and processing, as well as policy, ethics, and legal considerations. This manual also defines several considerations in the modelling phase, including AI algorithm design, as well as criteria to evaluate AI algorithms and AI-based products. It concludes the description of the suggested templates for *AI Management Checklist* and *AI Management Report*.

The policy, ethics and legal considerations are of significant importance given the nature of the problems that evolve around critical infrastructure protection, where sensitive data is at risk of being misused if not proper actions are taken to secure data exchange and communication channels.

1. Scope

The consortium of collaborating partners in PRECINCT project are exploring ways in which AI-based products/applications can benefit from standardised procedures and recommendation guidelines. This technical report describes key considerations that should guide the development of AI-based products including data management and administration, data pre and post-processing, policy, ethical and legal issues, as well as AI algorithm life cycle, and evaluation of AI-based products for critical infrastructure protection.

2. Normative references

Title	Description	Link
AI for Natural Disaster Management	This text “capitalizes on the growing interest and novelty of AI in the field of natural disaster management to help lay the groundwork for best practices in the use of AI for: assisting with data collection and handling, improving modelling across spatiotemporal scales, and providing effective communication.”	https://www.itu.int/en/ITU-T/focusgroups/ai4ndm/Pages/default.aspx

AI and Internet of Things for Digital Agriculture	The document seeks to “explore the potential of emerging technologies including AI and IoT in supporting data acquisition and handling, improving modelling from a growing volume of agricultural and geospatial data, and providing effective communication for interventions related to the optimization of agricultural production processes.”	https://www.itu.int/en/ITU-T/focusgroups/ai4a/Pages/default.aspx
AI for Autonomous and Assisted Driving	The document “supports standardization activities for services and applications enabled by AI systems in autonomous and assisted driving.”	https://www.itu.int/en/ITU-T/focusgroups/ai4ad/Pages/default.aspx
Machine Learning for Future Networks including 5G	This document aims at drafting “technical specifications for machine learning (ML) for future networks, including interfaces, network architectures, protocols, algorithms and data formats.”	https://www.itu.int/en/ITU-T/focusgroups/ml5g/Pages/default.aspx
AI for Health	This text seeks “to establish a standardized assessment framework for the evaluation of AI-based methods for health, diagnosis, triage or treatment decisions.”	https://www.itu.int/en/ITU-T/focusgroups/ai4h/Pages/default.aspx
EU guidelines on ethics in artificial intelligence: Context and implementation	“[T]his paper aims to shed some light on the ethical rules that are now recommended when designing, developing, deploying, implementing, or using AI products and services in the EU.”	https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/BRIE/2019/640163/EPRS_BRI(2019)640163_EN.pdf

3. Abbreviations and acronyms

5V	Volume, Velocity, Variety, Veracity, Value
AI	Artificial Intelligence
CI	Critical Infrastructure
CIP	Critical Infrastructure Protection
DataOps	Data Operations
DL	Deep Learning
EDA	Exploratory Data Analysis
FGDC	Federal Geographic Data Committee
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
ML	Machine Learning
MLOps	Machine Learning Operations

4. Potential challenges

Potential disruptive impacts of artificial intelligence are expected to challenge the design, implementation, and adoption of AI-based products in CIP and other fields. The first challenge commonly found is the digitization of processes of CI operations. Digital transformation is a required first step that clears the path to the adoption of AI solutions, demanding from CI operators an investment in the adoption of technologies that provide the foundation on top of which AI-based products are to be developed. In the presence of digitized processes, other challenges may arise, including data management and data security and privacy, which refer not only to the storage and management of data, but also to the transmission and exchange of data.

As large datasets are available, some questions may come up regarding the comprehensiveness and accuracy of the data. Large volumes of data do not necessarily translate into accurate and useful data; furthermore, some AI algorithms require labelled datasets, which in many cases, especially in large datasets, are most of the time unavailable.

AI algorithms also pose some challenges that include biases that can be introduced as a result of insufficient or inaccurate datasets, as well as human factors that affect the training of the models. Some types of algorithms, especially those based on artificial neural networks, do not follow processes typical of explainable artificial intelligence algorithms that allows human users to comprehend and trust the results created by the algorithm. Model transparency is another factor that is often underestimated, and sometimes misunderstood. Transparency should be introduced in every step of the workflow, starting at the data collection process, where detailed methodology of the data collection process should be provided, as well as the selection of the AI algorithm, and what was done to reduce the effect of bias in the model.

Modern AI-enhanced systems exhibit a challenge when it comes to integration with legacy systems. The deployment of AI models is not always a straightforward task, especially when models need to be maintained and updated due to the evolving condition of datasets used to train the models.

Declaring the ownership of AI-based products is also a commonly debated topic that confronts the different actors involved in the development of AI-based products. Should the partners that implement the algorithm hold the ownership, or does it belong to the

partners that provide the data? Misusing AI-enabled technologies is often a topic in the radar of ethic committees, especially when the presence of AI is ubiquitous.

Data

Data Management and Administration

Data management and administration refers to the process of collecting, organizing, storing, and protecting data. The following concepts indicate a variety of considerations that should be acknowledged in the process of data handling in AI-based products. Some of these concepts are more relevant in CIP due to the nature of the problem at hand, for example, data security and privacy, along with data sharing restrictions are key concepts in datasets collected from critical infrastructures. However, all the concepts should be considered in the process of identifying the right datasets for training AI models.

Data themes	minimum set of concepts used to label datasets in order to enable interoperability between different groups, companies, organizations, and nations.
Data provenance	data provenance records information on how data sets were generated, where the data came from originally, where it has been, and who handled it.
Data acquisition	process of collecting new data, converting, or transforming legacy data, sharing data, and purchasing data.
Data storage	describes what type, where and how hardware and software stores, deletes, backs up, organizes, and secures information. This includes a description of temporary and permanent storage.
Data elimination	defines rules that can be set up in a system for the removal of data. It includes removal from data broker or database following a clear and traceable protocol.
Data accessibility	provides a bridge between available data and the ability to use it. Data accessibility refers to the process that makes the available data suitable for use. This process includes data cleansing, reformatting, and standardization of data sets, as well as the implementation of access controls.
Data democratization	describes rules that complement data access with a comprehensive method to make data available to all the users indistinctly of the degree of expertise.
Data versioning	refers to tracking data sets by registering changes on a particular set of data. This includes naïve approaches such as saving entire datasets under completely new name of file path or the use of timestamps or unique IDs.

Metadata	refers to data or information about data. It is helpful to understand the structure, nature, and context of the data.
Data standards	define documented agreements on data representation, format, definition, structuring, transmission, manipulation, and management of data. Data standards are used for creating, sharing, and integrating data (e.g. ISO, FGDC, etc.).
File formats	refer to standard ways in which data is encoded for storage in a computer file. Define supported file formats and rules for file format conversion.
Data reusability	refers to the idea of using the same data set in different applications or scenarios. Data reusability provides consistency, reduces errors, saves time, and resources, and simplifies application development.
Data sharing restrictions	refers to the definition of guidelines concerning classified data and data sharing rules based on the level of accessibility of the data. Typical categories include <i>“general data”</i> for non-confidential and unclassified data sets, and <i>“classified”</i> category which may include <i>“restricted use/sensitive unclassified”</i> or <i>“strictly classified/secret”</i> data sets.
Data security	protective measures used to protect data against unauthorized access, ensuring data integrity and availability.
Data privacy	procedures for handling of data, including consent, notice, and regulatory obligations.
Data integrity	refers to the accuracy, quality, and completeness of data, which should be preserved over time.
Open Data	can be freely used, re-used, and redistributed by anyone. It must be available and accessible in a convenient and modifiable format and must be available for use by everyone.
Data validation	Ensures high-quality data by analysing whether data was recorded correctly, reflects realistic values, relevant data has no missing entries, and whether data follows established structure and format.
Data annotation	categorization and labelling of data used mainly for AI/ML applications. It is particularly useful for model training.
Data homogenization	is the process of bringing all the data into a unified and common framework to ensure consistency of data, integrity of analysis, and validity of results.
Data fusion	is the process of combining data from multiple sources to create a more complete dataset. It is useful to improve accuracy in AI models.

Synthetic data generation	refers to annotated information generated by computer simulations or algorithms as an alternative to real-world data.
Data bias	occurs when the data source is skewed, providing results that are not fully representative of the phenomenon.

Data Processing

The term data processing refers to the manipulation and transformation of digital data that can be used to deduce meaningful insights. Data processing covers a range of operations performed on data including manual or automated means.

Data curation	refers to the process of creating, organizing, and maintaining data sets by collecting from different sources and integrating them into repositories that are more valuable. The process involves collecting, structuring, indexing, and cataloguing data.
Data types	is an attribute from a piece of data that provides end-users with a specification on how to interact with the data.
Changes to the number of decimal positions	refers to the precision of a numeric value, which is important for the consistency of results in machine learning.
Data quality	measures the accuracy, completeness, validity, and consistency of data.
Missing values	occurs when an observation does not contain a value, either because it does not exist, or because it was lost due to errors in any part of the data management process.
Change in data units	refers to the use of different unit systems in the same dataset. This may cause inaccurate results in data analysis.
Data normalization	a way to rescale data so that each value falls between a range, usually between 0 and 1.
Data standardization	a way to rescale data so that each value is centered, and the unit is removed, usually using mean of 0 and standard deviation of 1.
Data denoising	refers to the process of smoothing data since data measured in engineering processes often contain different types and degrees of noise that may affect the accuracy of machine learning algorithms.
Data labelling	it is similar to data annotation. It is part of data pre-processing where raw data is contextualized with the addition of one or more labels. This is a necessary step for training supervised models.

Temporal data handling	refers to the process of managing data of moving things, events, or any observation that varies over time.
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Policy, Ethics, and Legal Considerations

In *EU guidelines on ethics in artificial intelligence: Context and implementation*¹, as well as in the *General Data Protection Regulation*², the European Union provides several key requirements for achieving trustworthy AI. The requirements include policy, ethics, and legal considerations that seek to protect the rights of end users to a proper use of automated data handling and processing in digital means.

General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)	Europe’s new data privacy and security law that provides regulatory points such as data protection principles, accountability, data security, data accessibility, and data consents.
Ethical approach	data ethics is a data-related practice that seeks to preserve the trust of persons that generate data, including users, patients, consumers, clients, employees, etc.
Transparent design	transparent data usage is key in the design of data products; it improves engagement from users.
Trustworthiness	criteria that measure the reliability of data to procure accurate AI models. The primary criteria to ensure trustworthiness includes credibility, confirmability, transferability, and dependability.
Impact assessment	data protection impact assessment is required under the GDPR, especially in projects that involve a “high-risk” to other people’s personal information.
Data sovereignty	concept that describes the legal parameters that affect data, particularly the idea that data are subject to the laws and governance structures of the nation where they are collected.
Government principles and guidelines	guidelines, recommendations, and best practices to ensure appropriate and effective data protection by design by data exploiters.

¹ [https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/BRIE/2019/640163/EPRS_BRI\(2019\)640163_EN.pdf](https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/BRIE/2019/640163/EPRS_BRI(2019)640163_EN.pdf)

² https://commission.europa.eu/law/law-topic/data-protection/data-protection-eu_en

Modelling

AI Algorithm Life Cycle

AI algorithm life cycle typically consists of three phases: design, development, and deployment. The phases include several stages that are iterative along the process. Deployment of AI models also requires continuous monitoring of performance since it tends to degrade as new information is available. The following considerations define the most common stages in the AI algorithm life cycle.

Project objectives	states the desired results of an AI project, including the motivation, direction, purpose, goals and deliverables.
Exploratory Data Analysis	a process that is used to understand data sets and summarize their main characteristics. It is a useful step that is required before any statistical analysis, and includes exploration, description, and summarizing data. This process ensures objectivity and interoperability. Typical steps in EDA include descriptive analysis, analysis of data types, missing values, outlier identification, correlations, identification of linear combinations, among others.
Machine learning pipeline	sequence of steps that the data must go through until it is effectively displayed to the end-users. Any ML project requires a minimum number of steps to prepare the data for the training of ML models and the postprocessing of the resulting output. Typical steps include data collection, data preparation, exploratory data analysis, training of the model, model evaluation, model deployment, and performance monitoring. These are the most basic steps of a ML pipeline.
Data acquisition	refers to the process of digitizing data from the context or environment for further storage and examination in a computer system.
Data preparation	refers to the process of cleaning, transforming, and restructuring data so that it can be used by ML/AI algorithms.
Data modelling	provides a common, consistent, and predictable way of defining and managing data resources across an organization. Data models may change.
Dimensionality reduction	is a pre-processing step that seeks to transform data into a more compact set of variables that maintaining the variance of the original data set. Dimensionality reduction is usually accomplished through unsupervised learning techniques.
Feature selection	is the process of reducing the number of input variables to a ML/AI model. The idea is to reduce computational

	cost as well as to improve the performance of the models.
Cross-validation	refers to a procedure commonly used to evaluate the true performance of learning models.
Parameter optimization	refers to the selection of parameters or hyper-parameters to improve the performance of a ML/AI model.
Model versioning	refers to the tracking and managing of changes in ML models over time.
Reusable software environments	refers to the development of reusable software components that can be used in the context of different software development lifecycles and architectural styles.
Model governance	e.g. who is publishing the model and when were models deployed, why changes are made, or when were de models used in production
Model monitoring	measures how well a ML model performs a task during training and in real-time deployment.
Model testing	ML model testing depends on software, but also on problem domain, datasets available, business context, and model selected.
Deployment of AI models	refers to the strategies for AI model deployment, which includes deployment on local machines, mobile devices, or cloud infrastructure.

AI Algorithm Selection

The selection of AI algorithms starts by identifying the category of the problem at hand and the objectives that have been defined by the users. The selection depends on a number of criteria, as described in the following definitions.

Problem categorization	categorizing the problem allows us to select the right algorithms to solve a problem. ML algorithms
Identifying applicable algorithms	algorithms can be broadly categorized into supervised (e.g. classification, regression) and unsupervised algorithms (e.g. clustering), transfer learning, reinforcement learning, deep learning.
AI algorithm selection	refers to the criteria to select the best AI algorithm. The selection depends on the problem at hand, available data, including quantity and quality of data. In other words, AI algorithm selection depends on the problem and the characteristics of the data.
Supervised learning	requires label datasets to train the ML models to classify observations or predict outcomes.
Unsupervised learning	ML algorithms capable of discovering hidden patterns without the need of labelled data or human intervention.

Transfer learning	refers to a technique that takes features learnt on a ML problem and leveraging it to a similar problem.
Reinforcement learning	an algorithm that follows a paradigm based on trial and error to solve problems. It is fundamentally rooted in the idea of learning the optimal behaviour in an environment to obtain a maximum reward.
Deep learning	refers to artificial neural networks that emulate the human brain to extract patterns hidden in a dataset. The term “deep” refers to artificial neural networks with three or more layers.

AI Algorithm Tunning

Knowledge of the types of AI algorithms available is important, but hyperparameter tuning is crucial for exploiting the capability of AI algorithms to identify useful and meaningful insights, trends, and patterns from data.

Hyperparameter optimization	seeks to find well-performing hyperparameter configuration of a machine learning algorithm on a dataset.
Ensemble learning	refers to a combination of several machine learning models to improve the ability to exploit patterns in a dataset.
Active learning	refers to a special case of supervised machine learning that seek to train high-performance classifier while keeping the size of the training dataset to a minimum.
Federated learning	allows collaborative training of decentralized models without sharing data (e.g. confidential data). Models can be trained over remote devices (e.g. servers) while keeping data localized.

Evaluation

Evaluation of AI Algorithms

Evaluation of performance of AI algorithms is a required stage in the AI algorithm life cycle that seeks to measure the trustworthiness of the results of the AI model. It considers some aspects such as time to build, train, and test, as well as other metrics related to accuracy, robustness in the presence of outliers, transparency, explainability, and interpretability.

Model performance	measures the accuracy and trustworthiness of a machine learning model (e.g. precision, accuracy, F1, etc.).
Baseline model	refers to a simple ML model that serves as a reference and as benchmarks for trained ML models. Baseline models can provide clues on future steps in a ML task.

Complexity	refers to properties of the machine learning algorithms that assess execution time and memory usage of a model.
Time to build, train, and test	refers to the time it takes to build, train, and test a machine learning algorithm.
Execution time	measures the efficiency of an algorithm in terms of execution time.
Robustness	refers to a type of metric that measures the reliability of a ML model. It measures the ability of a ML model to process new and independent observations.
Transparency	refers to a characteristic of ML models that allows an analyst to understand what the model is doing to the point of explaining it.
Explainability	refers to a set of techniques that describe the features that influence a prediction.
Interpretability	refers to a set of properties of a ML model that are useful to understand the outcome of the algorithm.
Scalability	refers to the ability of a ML model to handle varying loads of work, either due to a decrease of an increase of data observations.
Reliability	refers to any qualitative property (e.g. accuracy, availability, responsiveness) that assesses how well a ML model performs.

Evaluation of AI-based Products

Evaluation of AI-based products is complementary to evaluation of AI algorithms. On one hand, AI algorithms seek to exploit insights, trends, and patterns from datasets, thus, evaluating the performance of the algorithms gives an idea of the trustworthiness of the results. On the other hand, AI-based products refer to AI-enabled products where AI is a core component. Evaluation of AI-based products focuses more on the ethical use of AI models, the ownership, assuring the trustworthiness of the models by updating the AI models with new data.

Ethical use of AI models	<p>according to <i>Ethics By Design and Ethics of Use Approaches for Artificial Intelligence</i>³ published by the European Commission in 2021, AI-based systems/applications must preserve and promote:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • respect for human agency • privacy, personal data protection and data governance • fairness • individual, social, and environmental well-being • transparency
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³ https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/horizon/guidance/ethics-by-design-and-ethics-of-use-approaches-for-artificial-intelligence_he_en.pdf

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • accountability and oversight
Ownership of AI-based products	refers to decision of whether to use a model built and owned by a vendor, or a model that is built and owned by the end-user. There are important considerations that influence the ownership of AI-based products such as governance, model accuracy, and asset value.
Model documentation	refers to pertinent, complete, and proper documentation of how AI models were selected, trained, and deployed.
Track model performance	refers to the techniques used to track the performance of models both on training and validation datasets to reduce the risk of the model not performing well in production.
Model maintenance	describes the procedures that should be followed in the post-deployment of the model. AI models tend to degrade over time, thus retraining the model to consider new observations is a task that must be performed periodically. The process of model maintenance requires direct communication between data scientists and MLOps.

Appendix 1: AI Management Checklist

The AI management checklist serves as a tool to inspect the procedures followed in the development of AI-based products. The following checklist describes the suggested template to analyse the correct implementation of AI-based products.

Partner:	Conducted on (date and time):	Inspected by:	Location:
Context of the organization			

AI for Critical Infrastructure Protection		Auditor Name: José Carlos Carrasco Jiménez Date: 05-12-2022		
Data Management and Administration		Auditor		
Question	Response	Notes	Pass/Fail	Recommendations
Please provide details about the data themes used.				
Please provide details about data provenance (i.e. origin).				
Please provide details about the data acquisition process.				
Please provide details about the data storage process (i.e. how and where is data stored).				
Please provide details about the data elimination process.				
Please provide details about the data accessibility process (visibility + interoperability + usability).*				
Please provide details about the data versioning process.				
Please provide details about metadata (e.g. time of creation, definitions, annotations, etc.) and how it has been used.				
Please provide details about standards for creating, sharing, and integrating data (e.g. ISO, FGDC, etc.).				
Please provide details about conversion of file formats .				
Please provide details about data reusability (e.g. data formats, etc.).				
Please provide details about data sharing restrictions.				
Please provide details about the data security process.				
Please provide details about data privacy and how is sensitive data handled.				
Please provide details about data integrity assurance.				
Please provide details about Open Data sources used.				
Please provide details about the data validation process.				
If supervised learning was performed, please provide details about the data annotation process.				
Please provide details about the data homogenization process.				
Please provide details about the data fusion process.				
If sythetic data was used, please provide details about the synthetic data generation process.				
Please provide details about the data bias mitigation process.				

Data Processing		Auditor		
Question	Response	Notes	Pass/Fail	Recommendations
Please provide details about data curation procedures.				
Please provide details about changes of data types (e.g. numeric, date, character).				
Please provide details about changes to the number of decimal positions .				
Please provide details about data quality controls (e.g. outlier detection).				
Please provide details about missing values handling (e.g. completion, interpolation, deletion, imputation, etc.).				
Please provide details about change in data units .				
Please provide details about change in unit system (e.g. imperial vs metric).				
Please provide details about the data normalization process.				
Please provide details about the data standardization process.				
Please provide details about the data denoising process.				
Please provide details about the data labeling process.				

Policy, Ethics, and Legal Issues		Auditor		
Question	Response	Notes	Pass/Fail	Recommendations
Please provide details about the compliance with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) of the datasets used.				
Please provide details about the ethical approach used to guarantee the correct use of data to train AI models.				
Please provide details about the transparent design of AI technologies.				
Please provide details about the trustworthiness of the AI models.				
Please provide details about the impact assessment performed on the AI models.				
Please provide details about data sovereignty procedures.				
Please provide details of local government principles and guidelines followed in the data handling process.				

AI for Critical Infrastructure Protection		Auditor Name: José Carlos Carrasco Jiménez Date: 05-12-2022		
AI Algorithm Life Cycle		Auditor		
Question	Response	Notes	Pass/Fail	Recommendations
Please provide details about the project objectives .			Pass	
Please provide details about the machine learning pipeline used? Is it reproducible?				
Please provide an overview of the data acquisition and data preparation process.			Fail	
Please provide an overview of the model data .				
Please provide details about the dimensionality reduction process.				
Please provide details about the feature selection process.				
Please provide an overview of the parameter optimization process.				

Please provide details about model versioning system.	RSC was deployed in a Docker container through microservices that provide the version of the module being called.			
Please provide details about reusable software environments (e.g. conda, etc).				
Please provide details about the model governance (e.g. who is publishing the model and when were models deployed, why changes are made, or when were de models used in production).				
Please provide details about the model monitoring process (e.g. comparison of model input and output, performance metrics).				
Please provide details about the model testing environments used.				

AI Algorithm Selection		Auditor		
Question	Response	Notes	Pass/Fail	Recommendations
Please provide the details about problem categorization .				
Please provide details about the process for identifying applicable algorithms .				
Please provide details about the data and AI algorithm selection .				
Did you use supervised learning ? Please provide details about the algorithm and labeled dataset.				
Did you use unsupervised learning ? Please provide details about the algorithm used.				
Did you use transfer learning ? Please provide details.				
Did you use reinforcement learning ? Please provide details.				
Did you use deep learning ? Please provide details about the algorithm and architecture used.				

AI Algorithm Tunning		Auditor		
Question	Response	Notes	Pass/Fail	Recommendations
Did you perform hyperparameter optimization ? Please provide details.				
Did you perform ensemble learning ? Please provide details.				
Did you use active learning paradigm? Please provide details.				
Did you do federated learning ? Please provide details.				

AI for Critical Infrastructure Protection		Auditor Name: José Carlos Carrasco Jiménez Date: 05-12-2022		
Evaluation of AI Algorithms		Auditor		
Question	Response	Notes	Pass/Fail	Recommendations
Please provide details about the metrics used to measure the model performance (e.g. precision, accuracy, F1, etc.).			Pass	
Did you train a baseline model ? Did you compare your model with the baseline model? Please provide details.				
Did you test for complexity ? Please provide details.				
Did you record the times to build, train, and test ? Please provide details.			Fail	
Did you record the execution time (i.e. time to make predictions or inferences)? Was execution time within reasonable time? Please provide details.				

Did you test for robustness ? Did you add noise and tested your algorithm to test for robustness? Please provide details.				
Did you test for transparency ? Please provide details.				
Did you test for explainability ? Please provide details.				
Did you test for interpretability ? Please provide details.				
Did you test for scalability ? Please provide details.				
Did you test for reliability ? Please provide details.				

Evaluation of AI-based products		Auditor		
Question	Response	Notes	Pass/Fail	Recommendations
Please provide details about the ethical use of AI models.				
Please provide details about ownership of AI-based products.				
Did you prepare model documentation . Please provide details.				
Did you track model performance when the model was deployed in production environments? Please provide details.				
Please provide details about the model maintenance procedures (e.g. is your AI model retrained? How often?).				
Please provide details about the deployment of AI models.				

Appendix 2: AI Management Report

The AI management report template is an example of how the concluding remarks from the auditor could look like. The audit report includes information about the results of the inspection of AI-based products, the client, location, and date. It also highlights failed items that should be revised, along with some notes and recommendations that can be used by the client to improve the score of the audit.

<Client> | <Date> | <Auditor>

AI Management Checklist

Complete

Inspection score	Failed items	Due date
92.6%	6	21-01-2023

Client
<Client>
Conducted on
<Date> <Time>
Inspected by

<Auditor>
Location
Online

Failed items 4 failed

Data | Data Management and Administration

Please provide details about the data versioning process.	Fail
Notes	
Recommendations	

Please provide details about the data versioning process.	Fail
Notes	
Recommendations	

Please provide details about the data versioning process.	Fail
Notes	
Recommendations	

Data | Data Management and Administration

Please provide details about the data themes used.	Pass

...

Data | Data Processing

Please provide details about data curation procedures.	Pass

...

Data | Policy, Ethics, and Legal Issues

Please provide details about the compliance with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) of the datasets used.	Pass
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Modelling | AI Algorithm Life Cycle

Please provide details about the project objectives.	Pass

...

Modelling | AI Algorithm Selection

Please provide the details about problem categorization.	Pass

...

Modelling | AI Algorithm Tunning

Please provide the details about problem categorization.	Pass
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...

Evaluation | Evaluation of AI Algorithms

Please provide details about the metrics used to measure the model performance (e.g. precision, accuracy, F1, etc.).	Pass

...

Evaluation | Evaluation of AI-based products

Please provide details about the ethical use of AI models.	Pass

...

Recommendations	
Inspector's full name and signature	Date